

A Study of Vanadyl Ion in Acidified Ammonium Vanadate Solution. Part I

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Acidification of a solution of orthovanadate causes the formation of polyvanadates and finally that of cations VO_2^+ or VO^{3+} . The exact ratio of the acid at which the cation is formed in presence of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ and the composition of the precipitate of vanadylferrocyanide have been studied by following the monovariation method. The result of the analysis of vanadyl ferrocyanide corresponds with formula $\text{KVO}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$, confirming the nature of the cation to be VO^{3+} in the solid precipitate.

Vanadium, like molybdenum and tungsten, has a tendency to form polyacids and polysalts. Studies on decomposition of sodium and ammonium vanadates by mineral acids¹ reveal the formation of VO_2^+ or VO^{3+} on addition of 3-4 equivalents of acid. The present work has been undertaken to confirm the formation of the cation and to establish whether it is VO_2^+ or VO^{3+} .

EXPERIMENTAL

Formation of Vanadyl Ferrocyanide

Monovariation method², using specific conductance as a guide, was employed for the study. The results are shown in Fig. 1. Breaks in curves A and B are found at 3 and 4 equivalents of the acid. It seems that the first break in the curves corresponds to the isoelectric point and it is in accordance with the equation:

On adding more acid, the V_2O_5 formed tends to pass into VO_2^+ ion according to the equation:

There may be conversion of VO_2^+ into VO^{3+} without any consumption of acid due to existence of the equilibrium:

at the *pH* of the experiment.

The breaks in the curves in Fig. 1, corresponding to the addition of 4 equivalents of the acid, mark the completion of reaction (2) in which the cation VO_2^+ is formed. The precipi-

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1. Bhattacharya *et al.*, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1961, 30, 75, 79.

2. Nayar and Pandey, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 284.

pitape formed at this stage with potassium ferrocyanide, however, contains VO^{2+} , and not VO_2^+ as shown below.

FIG. 1. Effect of dilution.

A: Varying amounts of $M/30$ -HCl soln. added to 4 ml of $M/30$ -am. vanadate + 4 ml of $M/30$ - $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ soln. Total vol. = 35 ml in each case.
 B: Varying amounts of $M/40$ -HCl added to 4 ml of $M/40$ -am. orthovanadate + 4 ml of $M/40$ - $K_4Fe(CN)_6$. Total vol. = 35 ml in each case.

FIG. 2. Addition of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ to acidified am. vanadate soln.

Stoichiometry of Vanadyl Ferrocyanide

Monovariation method was employed for this study also. A series of samples was prepared by taking a constant volume (20 ml) of a mixture of 4 ml of $M/30$ ammonium vanadate and 16 ml of equimolar HCl, adding to it varying amounts of $M/30$ potassium ferrocyanide after allowing the mixture to stand for sometime and making the total volume constant by conductivity water. The experiment was repeated with $M/60$ solutions and the conductance measurement data were plotted.

In each case breaks are seen in the curves (Fig. 2, curves A,B) at one equivalent of potassium ferrocyanide, showing the composition of the precipitate either as $K_3VO_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ or $KVO[Fe(CN)_6]$.

The composition of the precipitate was determined by quantitative studies. Different volumes of ammonium vanadate solutions were acidified to convert the vanadate into vanadyl stage. Excess of potassium ferrocyanide was added to each solution for complete precipitation. The solutions were filtered through weighed sintered crucibles. The precipitates were weighed after filtration, washing, and drying at 100° and 400° respectively. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Wt. of vanadate.	Wt. of vanadium.	Wt. of ppt. expected if compound is		Wt of the precipitate obtained		
		$K_3VO_3[Fe(CN)_6]$.	$KVO[Fe(CN)_6]$	after drying in a desiccator.	at 100° .	at 400° .
0.1408 g.	0.04246 g.	0.4328 g	0.2650 g.	0.2850 g.	0.2850 g.	0.2650 g.
0.1877	0.05661	0.5771	0.3545	0.3538	0.3538	0.3538
0.0704	0.02123	0.2164	0.1329	0.1314	0.1314	0.1314

The weight of the precipitate obtained in each case corresponds to the formula $KVO [Fe(CN)_6]$, showing that the vanadyl ion present in the solid is VO^{3+} and not VO_2^+ . This has been further confirmed by dissolving a weighed amount of the precipitate in NaOH solution and titrating the resulting $Na_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ against a standard potassium permanganate solution. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Ppt.	$Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$ expected.	$Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$ obtained.
0.07632 g.	0.06084 g.	0.0507 g.
0.05231	0.03445	0.0339
0.01240	0.00826	0.0083

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